

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Supplementary Figure 1. Q-Q plots showing the distribution of observed versus expected $-\log_{10}(p)$ -values for Mg^{2+} in (A) base model – corrected for age, sex and PC1-3 - genomic inflation factor 1.003277, (B) model 1- corrected for age, sex, eGFR, PC1-3 - genomic inflation factor 1.003411, and (C) model 2 - corrected for age, sex, eGFR, HbA_{1c}, PC1-3 - genomic inflation factor 1.005874, in the Hoorn DCS cohort.

A

B

Supplementary Figure 2. Genome-wide $-\log_{10}(\text{p-value})$ plots from association analyses with serum Mg^{2+} concentration in 3,466 people with type 2 diabetes in the Hoorn, DCS study. (A) Adjusted for age, sex, PC 1-3 and eGFR and (B) Adjusted for age, sex, PC 1-3, eGFR and HbA_{1c} . Genome-wide significance ($P < 5 \times 10^{-8}$) is indicated by the red horizontal line. The blue line presents significance $p < 10^{-6}$. DCS= Diabetes Care System, eGFR= estimated glomerular filtration rate, HbA_{1c} = Hemoglobin A_{1c} , PC= principal component.

Supplementary Table 1. Adjusted models of associations between serum Mg²⁺ concentrations and the lead regional genome-wide significant SNPs.

SNP	chr	Location	Closest gene	% Variance explained	Model 1 ³ Beta (mmol/L)	Model 1 ³ SE	Model 1 ³ P	Model 2 ⁴ Beta (mmol/L)	Model 2 ⁴ SE	Model 2 ⁴ P
rs7894336	10	8026609	<i>TAF3</i>	0.53	-0.011	0.002	4.2E-9	-0.011	0.002	1.2E-9
rs11264341	1	155151493	<i>TRIM46</i>	0.47	0.010	0.002	1.3E-7	0.010	0.002	1.8E-7
rs10019833	4	77357592	<i>SHROOM3</i>	0.37	0.010	0.002	8.9E-7	0.009	0.002	1.6E-6
rs2270860	6	43270151	<i>SLC22A7</i>	0.31	-0.010	0.002	1.3E-6	-0.011	0.002	5.6E-8

¹Allele frequency is for European populations, according to the gnomAD database v3.1.2. (49). ²Coded alleles are inversely associated with serum Mg²⁺.

³Adjusted for age, sex, eGFR, PC1-3. ⁴Adjusted for age, sex, eGFR, HbA_{1c}, PC1-3.

Supplementary Table 2. Loci that display similar effect sizes and an identical direction of the effect on serum Mg²⁺ levels in people with type 2 diabetes (DCS cohort) and in a previous study focused on the general population.

SNP	EA	NEA	Gene	Meyer			DCS			Meta-analysis					
				Beta ¹	SE ¹	P ¹	Beta	SE	P	Beta	SE	P	Q_statistic	Q_P	i ²
rs4072037	C	T	MUC1	-0.010	0.001	2.01E-36	-0.009	0.002	6.99E-07	-0.010	0.001	6.87E-29	0.056813	0.811606	0
rs13146355	G	A	SHROOM3	-0.005	0.001	6.27E-13	-0.009	0.002	1.28E-06	-0.006	0.001	2.84E-11	4.102663	0.042816	0.76
rs11144134	T	C	TRPM6	-0.011	0.001	8.21E-15	-0.003	0.004	4.59E-01	-0.011	0.001	2.95E-27	4.452573	0.034849	0.78
rs3925584	C	T	DCDC5	-0.006	0.001	5.20E-16	-0.005	0.002	7.76E-03	-0.006	0.001	5.81E-11	0.137167	0.711114	0
rs10858940	C	T	ATP2B1	-0.007	0.001	1.05E-16	-0.005	0.002	2.00E-02	-0.007	0.001	2.64E-13	0.869574	0.351073	0
rs7197653	C	G	PRMT7	-0.005	0.001	2.02E-06	-0.008	0.003	5.95E-03	-0.005	0.001	1.77E-08	0.788627	0.374516	0
rs2592394	A	G	HOXD9	-0.004	0.001	4.61E-07	-0.002	0.002	2.44E-01	-0.004	0.001	4.05E-05	0.485471	0.485955	0
rs448378	G	A	MDS1	-0.004	0.001	1.25E-08	-0.003	0.002	1.23E-01	-0.004	0.001	2.09E-05	0.252665	0.615205	0
rs4561213	G	T	LUZP2	-0.004	0.001	2.60E-07	-0.003	0.002	1.17E-01	-0.004	0.001	1.97E-05	0.212603	0.644734	0

¹Data retrieved from Meyer *et al.*, 2010 ¹

chr= chromosome, DCS= diabetes care system, SE= standard error, SNP= single nucleotide polymorphism.

Supplementary Table 3. Loci associated with genetic variability according to GTEx consortium in skeletal muscle tissue.

SNP	chr	Location	Allele frequency ¹	Function	Coded ²	Closest gene	% Variance explained	Beta (mmol/L)	SE	P	Linked gene ³	NES ³	P ³
rs10795574	10	7948137	0.42	<i>Intronic</i>	A>G	<i>TAF3</i>	0.45	-0.009	0.002	2.5E-6	<i>ATP5F1C</i>	-0.073	9.4E-7
rs760077	1	155178782	0.40	<i>Missense</i>	A>T	<i>MTX1</i> or <i>THBS3</i>	0.60	0.010	0.002	4.6E-06	<i>THBS3</i>	-0.211	2.2E-19
rs2870238	4	77373079	0.49	<i>Intronic</i>	C>T	<i>SHROOM3</i>	0.51	0.010	0.002	4.0E-07	<i>CCDC158</i>	-0.200	4.0E-6
rs9394951	6	43350753	0.56	<i>None</i>	C>T	None	0.58	0.009	0.002	4.7E-06	<i>RPL7L1</i>	-0.098	4.9E-7

¹Allele frequency is for European populations, according to the gnomAD database v3.1.2. (49). ²Coded alleles are inversely associated with serum Mg²⁺. ³eQTL of skeletal muscle looked up in the GTEx consortium (50).

Chr= chromosome, GTEx= genotype-tissue expression, Mg²⁺= magnesium, NES= normalized affect size, PC= principal component, SE= standard error, SNP= single nucleotide polymorphism.

Supplementary Table 4. Loci associated with genetic variability according to human kidney meQTL and eQTM association analyses.

SNP	chr	Location	Coded	Closest gene	Linked gene	CpG	meQTL Beta ¹	meQTL P	eQTM Beta ²	eQTM P
rs11264341	1	155151493	C>T	<i>TRIM46</i>	<i>EFNA3</i>	cg23891169	0.578	3.2E-19	-0.136	2.0E-4
rs11264341	1	155151493	C>T	<i>TRIM46</i>	<i>MUC1</i>	cg13239514	-0.264	8.5E-9	-0.209	3.2E-11
rs10019833	4	77357592	T>C	<i>SHROOM3</i>	<i>STBD1</i>	cg05861031	-0.687	1.8E-32	-0.196	9.3E-6
rs10019833	4	77357592	T>C	<i>SHROOM3</i>	<i>SHROOM3</i>	cg12584791	-0.186	2.2E-8	-0.270	1.3E-11
rs2270860	6	43270151	C>T	<i>SLC22A7</i>	<i>POLH</i>	cg00050375	-0.365	7.3E-12	-0.085	2.6E-5
rs2270860	6	43270151	C>T	<i>SLC22A7</i>	<i>SLC22A7</i>	cg15360480	0.225	5.5E-7	-0.189	5.9E-5

All data was retrieved from https://susztaklab.com/Kidney_meQTL/index.php (28).

¹meQTL Beta is reported with respect to the alternate allele.

²eQTM Beta is reported as the association between CpG methylation and gene expression.

Chr= chromosome, eQTM= expression quantitative trait methylation, meQTL= DNA methylation quantitative trait locus, PC= principal component, SNP= single nucleotide polymorphism, STD= standard deviation.

Supplementary Table 5. Traits associated with genetic variability according to the Open GWAS database.

SNP	chr	Location	Coded	Population	Trait	Beta	SE	N	P
rs7894336	10	8026609	C>T	European	phosphate	-0.013	0.002	314658	6.3E-8
rs11264341	1	155151493	C>T	European	urea	-0.041	0.002	344052	3.3E-71
rs10019833	4	77357592	T>C	European	cystatin C	0.062	0.002	344264	2.5E-173
rs2270860	6	43270151	C>T	European	cystatin C	-0.032	0.002	344264	1.1E-40

All data was retrieved from the Open GWAS database (29).

Chr= chromosome, SNP= single nucleotide polymorphism.